

THE INTERPHASE CHEMISTRY OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The modification of carbon fibre surface has oxidative treatments prior to incorporation into polymeric matrices is now well understood from both a chemical and a morphological point of view. Careful work by XPS and AFM has provided a detailed picture of the fibre surface prior to its interaction with the matrix resin. The study of the nature of the actual interactions themselves is rather more demanding and requires careful experimental approaches to present model or real composites in such a way that a surface chemical analysis can be obtained from the interface, or more correctly interphase region. This paper describes two methods that have been developed in recent years in the author's laboratory.

The traditional manner of quantifying the adsorption characteristics of an adsorbate on a solid surface is by the determination of adsorption isotherms. This is traditionally carried out from the gas phase or from the liquid phase by monitoring the depletion of adsorbate in solution. It is shown that by using XPS or ToF-SIMS it is possible to determine adsorption isotherms by quantitative evaluation of the amount of adsorbate in place on the solid surface. This approach has been applied to the adsorption of medium molecular weight PMMA, DGEBA and an amine curing agent on carbon fibres in their untreated state and following different level of surface treatment. The results, rather unexpectedly, show that adsorption of PMMA and the amine curing agent are unaffected by the level of surface treatment but that the uptake of DGEBA is greatly enhanced.

Forensic analysis of failed composite fracture surfaces can tell us much about interface integrity, but is hampered by the contamination of freshly exposed surfaces by hydrocarbon contamination from the atmosphere, a particular problem in the vicinity of grease coated lead screws of tensile testing machines! We have designed and manufactured miniature Mode I and Mode II test rigs that are readily incorporated into auxiliary vacuum chambers on our ToF-SIMS systems. This enables fracture under controlled conditions to be obtained and ToF-SIMS analysis to be carried out without exposure to the ambient atmosphere. Data obtained from CFRP specimens tested as manufactured and following environmental exposure is described.

KEYWORDS: interphase, XPS, ToF-SIMS, adsorption isotherms, *in-situ* fracture, carbon fibres, epoxy matrix

ADSORPTION OF MATRIX MOLECULES

The construction of adsorption isotherms from the gas phase is a well-known technique in classical surface chemistry. The study of adsorption from the liquid phase is, however, less straightforward since both solute and solvent compete for the same adsorption sites on the substrate. The study of liquid phase adsorption is usually accomplished by solution analysis but this yields only relative adsorption isotherms. The solution to this difficulty is to measure the amount of material adsorbed on the solid substrate directly using surface specific analysis methods such as X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and time of flight secondary ion mass spectrometry (ToF-SIMS) (1).

In the measurement of gas phase adsorption it is convenient to express the amount adsorbed in terms of the fractional coverage, θ :

$$\theta = \frac{\left[\text{number of adsorption sites occupied} \right]}{\left[\text{total number of sites available} \right]}$$

Which will often be expressed as the volume of adsorbate adsorbed by the solid surface, V at a particular gas pressure relative to the volume of adsorbate corresponding to monolayer coverage, although as we shall see later any convenient unit may be used. Thus:

$$\theta = \frac{V}{V_{\infty}}$$

Adsorption may be classified as physisorption or chemisorption, depending on the bond energies involved. All gases near their critical temperature tend to adsorb as a result of weak, non-specific secondary forces, and this is the basis of the well known BET method for the determination of the specific surface of finely divided solids. The enthalpy of adsorption for physisorption is generally considered to be less than -25 kJ mol^{-1} . When the adsorption energy is comparable to the energy of chemical bonds the process is referred to as chemisorption and enthalpies of adsorption are greater than 40 kJ mol^{-1} . A critical difference between the two classes of adsorption are their response to heat; in the case of physical adsorption the amount of material adsorbed reduces, whilst for chemical adsorption it increases. In relation to adhesion studies we are clearly only concerned with chemical adsorption, and an indication of the manner in which adsorption data can be treated was presented by Langmuir in 1918 (3).

In his model Langmuir made several assumptions:

- (1) Adsorption cannot proceed beyond monolayer coverage,
- (2) All adsorbent (substrate) sites are equivalent,
- (3) The adsorption at particular sites is not influenced by the occupation (or otherwise) of neighbouring sites.

This led to the definition of fractional coverage in the following form:

$$\theta = \frac{bP}{1 + bP}$$

If we replace V , to indicate the volume of gas adsorbed with the more general term Γ , and rearrange the equation as follows:

$$\frac{P}{\Gamma} = \left(\frac{1}{b\Gamma_m} \right) + \left(\frac{P}{\Gamma_m} \right)$$

where b is the ratio of rate constants for adsorption and desorption.

In the case of adsorption from the liquid phase, in which the substrate is removed from solution of concentration c , and the surface concentration of adsorbate, x , is measured by XPS or ToF-SIMS this equation becomes:

$$\frac{c}{x} = \left(\frac{1}{b\Gamma_m} \right) + \left(\frac{c}{\Gamma_m} \right)$$

Thus a plot of uptake, x , against solution concentration, c , will yield a curve, the adsorption isotherm, which, in principle, allows the calculation of the capacity of the surface for the adsorbate involved. Of course not all adsorption processes follow Langmuir's model and a test of conformity of the adsorption data can be made by plotting c/x against c . A straight line will result in the case of Langmuir adsorption with a gradient of $1/\Gamma_m$ and an intercept on $1/b\Gamma_m$.

This philosophy has been applied to study the interaction of matrix materials, adsorbed from dilute solutions, onto carbon fibre surfaces anodically oxidised at different treatment levels. Both thermosetting and thermoplastic matrix materials have been investigated (2), poly(methyl methacrylate) has been chosen as a typical thermoplastic material and the diglycidyl ether of

bisphenol A (DGEBA) and an amine curing agent have been taken as typical constituents of an epoxy matrix. The adsorption isotherms for these materials are shown in Figure 1, and the rather surprising observation is the apparent insensitivity of the PMMA molecules (Figure 1a) and the amine curing agent (Figure 1b) to the degree of fibre treatment. The DGEBA molecules, however, show a well defined step in adsorption characteristics between the untreated and the two treated batches of carbon fibres as indicated in Figure 1c. This observation reflects the universal observation that a critical level of surface treatment is required to achieve the optimum mechanical properties. In this case that level was around 25%, above which level of treatment the ILSS shows no noticeable improvement. Subsequent analysis of the data of Figure 1 showed that the adsorption of all three molecules on the fibre surface conformed to the Langmuir equation (2).

Figure 1. ToF-SIMS data for organic molecules adsorbed on carbon fibres, (a) PMMA, (b) amine curing agent, (c) DGEBA.

Further exploration of the exact nature of the chemistry of interfacial bonding can be achieved by careful analysis of specimens taken from the adsorption isotherm. An example of this approach, taken from our work on the structural adhesive bonding of aluminium, shows that ToF-SIMS can identify the formation of a covalent bond between organosilane treated aluminium and a dilute solution of a commercial adhesive manufactured for aerospace applications (3).

Thus by combining the two approaches it is, in principle, possible to estimate the relative aeric density of bonding sites as a function of surface treatment as well as the nature (and by implication the strength) of the bond that is formed between adsorbate and substrate.

IN SITU FRACTURE STUDIES BY TOF-SIMS

ToF-SIMS has been used to characterise a number of different epoxy resins formulations used in the fabrication of CFRPs. A fingerprint analysis of the bulk resin has been achieved using a novel sample preparation technique. Large blocks of bulk epoxy resin were microtomed to yield thin (~10µm) slices of material. Such specimens do not pose any of the usual electrostatic charging problems that may be encountered in the analysis of large slabs of cross-linked polymeric material. Such an approach ensures that the secondary ion yield, and hence the quality of the resultant spectrum, remains high. A typical spectrum, acquired using a VG Scientific Type 23 system equipped with a pulse ⁶⁹Ga⁺ ion source and a to stage reflectron analyser, is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Negative ToF-SIMS spectrum of a thin slice of DGEBA epoxy resin.

In order to study segregation and depletion phenomena at fibre surfaces the forensic examination of CFRP fracture surfaces is recommended. There are potential difficulties in this approach, however, in that the very surface sensitivity of XPS and ToF-SIMS can present problems if the fracture surface has been inadvertently contaminated following failure. In order to overcome such difficulties work of this type in the author's laboratory has always sought to carry out the fracture of composites and adhesive

joints within the ultra high vacuum of the surface analysis system. Initial work was carried out using impact fracture stages or tensile stages of uncertain geometry and loading configurations. More recently, however, stages have been designed that allow fracture surfaces to be generated under controlled conditions, viz Mode I and Mode II loading. Modification of the entry lock of a ToF-SIMS spectrometer, combined with specially designed stubs and a linear drive, has enabled an *in-situ* fracture stage to be produced that allows fracture surfaces of CFRP to be generated under different modes of loading (4). The design of the stages built to accomplish Mode I loading is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the Mode I *in situ* loading configuration.

The Mode I specimens are based on reduced size compact tension specimens (approximately 2cm in size), whilst the Mode II specimens are miniature 10° off-axis coupons. Both designs are based around the usual sample mounting procedure for our ToF-SIMS systems which a 1cm diameter SEM-type stub. Each fracture surface can be examined without the need to break vacuum, the sample being manipulated, in the usual manner, in the UHV of the spectrometer. The topographies of failures associated with the two modes of loading using these testing devices, compared with the full size test piece tested in the usual manner in a tensile testing machine, is shown in Figure 4. The close similarity in morphology between the miniature, *in-situ*, test pieces and the full size examples is clearly evident.

Figure 4. Electron micrographs of typical CFRP fracture surfaces.

(a) Mode I *in-situ*, (b) compact tension specimen, (c) Mode II *in-situ*, (d) 10° off axis coupon

Both Mode I and Mode II failure surfaces exhibit fragments of matrix adhering to the fibre but there are large regions, particularly in the case of the Mode I failure, where the fibre seems to be devoid of such residue. A positive ToF-SIMS spectrum recorded from such a region of a fracture surface (of a HTA/F922 composite) is shown in Figure 5, which is remarkably similar to that from the bulk matrix (not shown).

Figure 5. A typical positive ToF-SIMS spectrum of a Mode I specimen fractured in vacuum.

For comparison the spectrum from a similar *in-situ* compact tension specimen, that has been test in atmospheric conditions, is shown in Figure 6 and the lack of detail and inferior counting statistics compared with the *in-situ* failure is clearly seen.

Figure 6. A typical positive ToF-SIMS spectrum recorded from an in-situ Mode I coupon, fractured in atmospheric conditions.

The *in-situ* approach described above was used to study the environmental degradation of a CFRP system. Coupons were exposed to 85% RH at 50°C for three months, moisture uptake during this treatment led to an increase in mass of 0.8 – 1.0%. ToF-SIMS analysis of samples fractured within the ToF-SIMS system showed that the fibre/matrix interfacial bond had been compromised to a certain extent and the resultant spectra were now characteristic of the fibre surfaces prior to incorporation in the matrix. A positive ToF-SIMS spectrum from a Mode I fracture surface tested in situ is shown in Figure 7 (5), ions indicative of the carbon fibre surface are clearly seen in the low mass region. These studies were undertaken using a different system from the studies described above (HTA/F297).

Figure 7. Positive ToF-SIMS spectrum from an aged coupon fractured *in-situ* under mode I loading.

Further studies are planned with the conversion of the fast entry air lock of the spectrometer to an environmental chamber and the extension of the fracture studies to DCB geometries for adhesively bonded systems.

CONCLUSIONS

Surface analysis methods, such as XPS, have been widely used in the analysis of carbon fibre surfaces but have made little progress in the analysis of the interphase chemistry of CFRP systems. The use of ToF-SIMS to address this problem is shown to be a profitable and informative way of gaining access to such information, provided the necessary preparatory techniques are employed. It has been shown that the construction of adsorption isotherms, of dilute solutions of matrix materials adsorbed on carbon fibre surfaces, enables the chemisorption process to be unambiguously identified. Perhaps more importantly, the effect of different levels of surface treatment on the capacity of a solid surface for the adsorbate molecules can be determined.

Fractography by scanning electron microscopy is widely practiced but tells us nothing about the vanishingly thin layers of matrix material that may remain adhering to the fibre surface following failure. The development of a novel *in-situ* approach to fracture prior to the analysis of failure surfaces by ToF-SIMS has been described. Typical results from as fabricated and CFRP exposed to a high relative humidity show that such an approach enables the locus of failure to be defined very precisely.

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